

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Ursad****FIRST NAME: Khalif****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)
The author used the following software: MS-word 2013

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which one of the following statements is not true about the style guide?**
 - Style can encompass the usage of symbols.
 - Style can encompass the usage of the manuscript layout.
 - Style is just the usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary.¹**
 - Style can encompass the usage of an abbreviation.

2. **Which one of the following is true for American English?**
 - Uses quotation marks for citations.²**
 - Dear Mr Smith.

¹ Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. 2nd Ed.* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019) 24.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 49.

- Assumes collective names as plural.
 - Periods and commas are always outside the closing quotation mark.
3. ----- are included general encyclopedias and dictionaries, as well as newspapers and magazines.
- Primary sources.
 - Tertiary sources.³
 - Secondary source.
 - Think first.
4. ----- When you can represent what a source says more clearly or pointedly than it does.
- Summarize.
 - Quote.
 - Paraphrase.⁴
 - Note.
5. Which one of the following is the correct order for the bibliography of books with a single author or editor according to Turabian style?
- Author's first name and last name, publication information, the title of the book.

³ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th Ed. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013) 24.

⁴ Turabian, 49.

- Authors last name, author's first name. Title of the book: subtitle of the book. Publication information.**⁵
- Author's last and first name, publication information, and title of the book.
- Title of the book, author's last and first name, and publication information.
6. **All are the basic reason for citation, except**
- To give credit to the researcher.
- To assure readers about the accuracy of your fact.
- To show a reader the research tradition that informs your work.
- None.**⁶
7. **Which one of the following is true for qualitative research?**
- Usually involves some form of pre-test and post-test.
- Descriptive.
- Case study.**⁷
- Hypothetic deductive.
8. ----- is applied to describe current conditions, investigate relationships, and study cause-effect phenomena.

⁵ Turabian, 91.

⁶ Turabian, 86.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008) 13.

- Qualitative research.
- Narrative research.
- Case study research.
- Quantitative research.**⁸

9. **Which one of the following word is in the French language?**

- Correspondence.
- Existent.**⁹
- Address.
- Negligible.

10. **Which one of the following is true for the Official Journal of the European Union?**

- The L series contains EU notices and information.
- The C series contains EU legislations.
- The S series contains public procurement notices.**¹⁰
- The A-series contains EU Treaties.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 14.

⁹ European Commission and Directorate-General for Translation, *European Commission Style Guide English. English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2011), 7.

¹⁰ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, 68.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.